

STUDY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF VERTICAL GARDENS AND SAMARKAND LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE APPLY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6518008>

Annotation: The main purpose of the article is to study the development of vertical gardens and their application in the landscape architecture of Samarkand, the creation of modern projects and the development of scientific proposals for the improvement of the concept of landscape, beauty, nature in modern landscape design. consists of. The art of gardening is to prove that the architectural and planning features of modern vertical gardens, landscape and water compositions are formed in harmony, geometric proportion and harmony.
Keywords: vertical garden, recreational, architectural, composition, garden-park, ecological priority, landscape, historical-national, green wall, design.

Today, in the practice of recreational activities in the world, the environmentally friendly direction that creates the environment, integrates architecture with nature, creates a composition of open spaces - landscape architecture is developing rapidly, and gardening is actively developing as an ecologically priority and cost-effective direction. . Today there is a scientific and theoretical need to study effective methods of shaping landscape architecture and based on historical and national traditions.

An integrated approach to the study of ways of formation and development of national parks, the definition of the laws of their planning and historical solution, the experience of repairing and reconstructing existing historical parks is important in scientific research on the rational use of the traditions of garden-park construction. The lack of comparative study of ancient gardens, the lack of modern innovative directions in the design, the incomplete formation of landscape composition and historical sources in the creation of national parks, the complex of promising directions and effective ways of developing traditional garden art As a result of the lack of study, a number of problems arise, including the lack of urban planning requirements and regulations aimed at further improving and developing the landscape architecture of Uzbekistan, improving the quality of their planning solutions.

Figure 1. The project of vertical landscaping of the city hotel "PARKROYAL on Riskegipdv" was carried out by the oasis Archbureau (Singapore)

Figure 2. Solaris Research and Development Business Park in Singapore designed by architect Ken Eang

During the years of independence, the country has created ample opportunities for the development of landscape architecture and pays special attention to the further improvement of garden and park art. In this regard, architects are faced with the task of restoring the ancient methods of urban planning, including traditional garden-park art, in the redevelopment of urban and rural landscape architecture [1].

It should be noted that one of the ways to address such pressing issues in improving the landscape architecture of Uzbekistan is the great attention paid to the need to revive the Timurid garden art.

It is necessary to study the development of vertical gardens, modern assessment and develop principles for the implementation of landscape architecture in cities and villages of Uzbekistan. The world-famous gardens of our ancestors, created on the basis of landscape design, are based on the development and improvement of modern methods that can reflect our national traditions, national values, based on national ideas, miniature images and worldviews in classical literature.

The novelty in the study of the development of vertical gardens is the application to the landscape architecture of Samarkand and the creation and use of modern projects, improving the concepts of landscape, beauty, nature, using modern methods of modern landscape design.

In the creation of garden art, the architectural and planning features of vertical gardens, landscape and water compositions, which have not been preserved until now, prove that they are formed in mutual proportion, geometric proportionality and harmony.

The modern results and importance of vertical gardens is to expand and enrich knowledge in the field of modern vertical garden-park.

It is explained by the great importance of teaching vertical garden-parks in the implementation of project proposals in the teaching of the subjects "Garden-park art", "Landscape architecture and design" in higher education institutions, in project organizations.

Figure 3 WOHA School of Art in Singapore

The aim is to repair and restore existing parks in the practice of vertical gardening in all cities and regions of the country, to give them a national character, to design and create new types of modern national parks and to study architecture and urban planning, landscape architecture, landscape design and is based on the use of educational specialties in the educational process.

Vertical garden. A vertical garden (green wall, living wall) is a phytoval system or a single phytoval that represents a collection of living plants placed vertically in special structures.

The vertical garden is used to decorate both exterior walls, roofs and various structures of buildings, as well as interiors. The idea of a vertical garden is mostly in Paris by French botanist and designer Patrick Blanc. The first vertical installation was created in 1988.

The structures of vertical gardens are distinguished by materials, communication systems, fasteners, technological features, while maintaining the general principle of vertical orientation, the existence of a life support system. Plants for a vertical garden are selected depending on the specific conditions and a particular artistic solution, in any case, they usually try to use small or dwarf species with a height of 30-35 cm.

In the interior design, mainly tropical plant species are used, but the exterior design requires plants that can withstand the external climatic conditions.

Tasks [edit | edit code]

Green walls are often found in urban conditions where plants lower the overall temperature of the building. “The main reason for heat accumulation in cities is insolation, absorption of solar radiation by city roads and buildings and the accumulation of this heat in the building material and subsequent re-irradiation. sometimes they cool down.”[1]

Living walls can also be a means of reusing water. Plants can purify slightly contaminated water (e.g., gray water) by absorbing dissolved nutrients. Bacteria mineralize organic ingredients to grow in plants. Research using the GSky Pro wall system is underway at the Bertshi School in Seattle, Washington, but no public data is available at this time.

Living walls are very suitable for cities, especially because of the efficient use of existing vertical surfaces. They are also suitable for arid areas because the circulating water in the vertical wall evaporates less than in the horizontal gardens.

The living wall can also be used in urban farming, urban gardening, or as an art for its beauty. Sometimes it is built indoors to relieve sick building syndrome.

Living walls are also designed to restore poor air quality both indoors and outdoors.

Green walls provide an additional layer of insulation, which can protect buildings from heavy rainwater, resulting in strong storm water management and heat mass. They also help lower the temperature of the building as the vegetation absorbs a lot of sunlight.

This can reduce energy consumption and purify the air of VOC (volatile organic compounds) that emit paints, furniture and adhesives. Gases emitted from VOCs can cause headaches, eye irritation, respiratory tract and indoor air pollution.

Green walls can also remove mold from the inside of buildings, which can cause asthma and allergies. Plants within green walls can mitigate the effects of heat island and contribute to urban biodiversity [2].

Closed green walls can have a therapeutic effect on the plant. The aesthetic feel and appearance of green walls is another example of the benefits, but it affects the indoor climate with reduced CO2 levels, reduced noise levels and air pollution [3] [4].

However, in order to have an optimal effect on the indoor microclimate, it is important that the green wall plants have the best conditions for growth, both in irrigation and feeding, and with the required amount of light. To achieve the best results in all of the above areas, some green wall systems have special and patented technologies developed for the benefit of plants.

In urban areas, green walls also provide acoustic protection and reduce noise by absorbing sound.

Thomas Pew, a biogeochemist at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology in Germany, created a computer model of a green wall with a variety of plants. Studies have shown that the green wall absorbs nitrogen dioxide and particulate matter. In street canyons where polluted air is trapped, green walls can absorb polluted air and clear the streets.

In conclusion, as the basis of ecological style, decoration opens up radically new horizons in the ability to plant plants and their landscape design. Draping cold stone and concrete is to give it warmth and life.

Insonga xos go'zallikka bo'lgan intilish doimo ishonchli, funktsional, ammo jonsiz va estetik ko'rinishini yangi imkoniyatlarini izlashga undaydi.

But modern decoration technologies, the best facade paints, the latest achievements in the field of exterior and interior decoration can not be compared with the perfection of living nature. It is everyone's dream that we not only spend our weekends and walks in the garden, but also be in the lap of nature that amazes us every day and at home. First of all, it's about enjoying the beauty of the plants.

List of used literature:

1. APPENDIX 1 to the Provision on methodology of the organization of parks and green zones
2. (National Database of Legislation, 20.08.2018, No. 09/18/671/1776; 29.12.2019, No. 09/19/1046/4242; 14.12.2020, 09/20 / 777/1620-son)
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